

The Role of Social Media in Shaping Public Opinion in Society

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Abstract: Social media has succeeded in influencing public opinion in all societies, especially as public opinion now occupies a prominent position, having been almost absent forcibly at the hands of ruling regimes. Over the past era, social media platforms have acquired a role by adopting innovative forms of communication, applying them in various fields and for various purposes. This goes beyond merely acquiring new followers or establishing a wide network of communication. Social media has begun to make a qualitative impact by attracting more mature audiences, transforming into a primary media channel that plays a significant role in disseminating news and influencing public sentiments.

Social media has evolved into a fast-paced means of information delivery and event coverage, making it a center of attention and focus not only for the general public but also for traditional readable and audible media outlets. Comparing traditional visual and written media's ability to shape public opinion with the capabilities of this emerging form of online media, often referred to as the fourth estate, it can be argued that social media has relatively overshadowed its historical luster. This is not due to bias or any other reason, but rather because traditional media, whether newspapers or television channels, being funded and under the sponsorship of specific entities, parties, or prominent figures, is sufficiently bound by these affiliations. Social media, on the other hand, has surpassed and outperformed traditional media in terms of independence and liberation from obstacles and affiliations.

Keywords: Social media, Facebook, public opinion, societal issues.

Introduction:

Today, social media has become the focus of attention for many scholars in the fields of communication, political science, and social sciences. This heightened interest is a result of the significant role these platforms play in numerous global events, particularly in political, social, and even economic contexts. Social media has emerged as a prominent tool for mobilization, organization, and advocacy in various events, thanks to its numerous features, especially its ease of dissemination, usage, and rapid information exchange.

Concepts related to virtual communities have gained attention, with academic interest increasing in issues related to social networks and virtual communities since the internet has become an integral part of daily life for individuals and groups. In recent times, societies have undergone various transformations and changes across social, cultural, political, and economic dimensions, impacting their structure, composition, and stability⁽¹⁾. No one can deny the contribution of modern communication channels, particularly social media, to these global societal changes.

The advent of interactive media (social media) has altered many concepts associated with media and communication. These channels have evolved from being mere entertainment to becoming influential tools in shaping public opinion and transforming prevailing social norms. Gradually, their role has

⁽¹⁾ Zaki, M. (2005). "The Small Screen and Its Impact on Children's Behavior." *Journal of Education*, Issue 154, Thirty-Fourth Year, National Committee for Education, Culture, and Sciences, Qatar, p. 264

grown in knowledge creation, information dissemination, challenging prevailing social patterns, and imposing their vision on changing the shape and style of social relationships.

Individuals within these media platforms play dual roles as both recipients and senders, potentially being observers or active participants who possess a unique perspective on a topic, document moments, or even create events. This emphasizes the role of interactive media in constructing social realities⁽²⁾. This new type of media, as some call it, not only contributed to the rise of an interactive and instantaneous branch of media but also introduced new forms that are no longer anchored to a fixed structure. Instead, they rely on the concept of the environment, functioning as a virtual space where all forms of relationships, reflections, behaviors, interactions, and expressions occur without significant control from public authorities. The ability of authorities to restrain or limit these phenomena through laws and regulations has become increasingly challenging, as these virtual spaces operate with relative autonomy.

Research Topic:

Undoubtedly, social media networks can serve as effective intermediaries in influencing and increasing political awareness and in changing certain issues, benefiting and harming political actors alike. Politicians employ various communication strategies, with some investing in multiple platforms, where Facebook and Twitter remain the most significant. These diverse communication strategies, by their nature, remain open and simulate the public itself, primarily targeting active voters on social networks who can influence campaigns and participate by disseminating ideas. These platforms may play a role in serving candidates with potential by announcing their electoral programs and addressing voters and the public through these channels.

In our present time, social media platforms play a significant role in directing, shaping, and influencing public opinion, serving as the nerve center of contemporary life. Given their role and impact on various public policies, they wield a double-edged sword. On one hand, they contribute positively to forming a public opinion characterized by positivity towards various societal issues. On the other hand, they have a negative aspect, working to fragment and corrupt society and the minds of the youth⁽³⁾.

The influence on public opinion occurs through various steps and methods. Social media, as a crucial source of information, continually provides the audience with vast amounts of diverse data and knowledge on various issues and topics. This information may be accurate within its natural context, stripped of context, changed in meaning, incomplete and distorted, or intentionally directed. Modern social media has also facilitated global connections, transcending political and geographical boundaries and cultural isolation experienced by many human societies. Our contemporary world witnesses significant changes in communication technology that impact political and economic relations and thought patterns in different societies.

In this context, social media platforms are considered important and primary factors that have contributed to political processes and social movements. They have broken the barrier of fear and media silence in traditional channels, particularly in the Arab world. Additionally, they serve as a means of communication and intersection between global and local dynamics. Interactions occur against the backdrop of the global context, with their variables unfolding at the local level. This happens through social changes, focusing on the formation of friendships and group memberships. Political changes manifest in the fact that the political landscape has become a fundamental variable for these networks, integrating political interactions between the real world and the parallel world represented by widely spread social media in the virtual space. The prominent impact of social media is evident, particularly from political perspectives.

⁽²⁾ Salem Sari, Khedr Zakaria, "Contemporary Social Issues: Globalization and the Production of New Problems," Al-Awla'i Publishing and Distribution, Damascus, 1st edition, 2004, pp. 196 and onwards.

⁽³⁾ Reference: Medhat Abu Al-Nasr Medhat, "Concept, Objectives, and Characteristics of Social Media Networks, and Monitoring the Positives and Negatives," Conference on the Regulations of Using Social Media in Islam, Volume 1, Saudi Islamic University Press, November 22-23, 2016, p. 2

The prominent impact of social media is clearly evident in political aspects, and this can be substantiated in three points:

1. **Public Opinion Mobilization:** Groups present on social media networks play an effective role in mobilizing public opinion on political, social, and economic issues. For example, these networks have become a platform for protests and rallies, opening a new avenue for political advertising, presenting electoral programs, and garnering support.
2. **Emergence of Virtual Citizenship:** Social media platforms have opened the space for exercising citizenship issues online. The virtual community becomes a realm for exercising rights and advocating for them.
3. **Activation of the Civil Society's Role:** Social media networks contribute to increasing the activation of the civil society's role. Numerous organizations have established their presence in the virtual community, utilizing these networks to grow their memberships and invite beneficiaries to participate in their programs⁽⁴⁾.

Study Questions:

The current research aims to answer a fundamental question, which is, "What role do social media, especially Facebook, play in creating and shaping public opinion in society?" This primary question can branch into secondary questions, including:

- Where does the ability of social media platforms lie in mobilizing large numbers of individuals around a specific topic and a particular direction?
- To what extent can political benefit be derived from the mechanisms of public opinion formation on social media platforms?

Research Objectives: This research aims to:

- Shed light on the impact of social media platforms in shaping and creating public opinion and their role in influencing societal issues.
- Highlight the significance held by platforms like Facebook and Twitter in our contemporary era and their influence on various societal issues.
- Identify the influencing factors in crystallizing public opinion among individuals in society and investigate the importance of social media platforms in influencing those in positions of power and subsequently intervening in critical decisions.
- Recognize the significance of Facebook as a tool for advocacy aiming to support social and humanitarian causes.

Importance of the Study:

The significance of the current research lies in shedding light on one of the modern communication mechanisms with widespread global popularity, namely social media platforms. It explores the extent of their impact on individuals. Despite the positive effects of these platforms, they also exhibit numerous highly influential negative effects on society. This warrants the establishment of regulations and standards to govern the use of social media platforms. Scientifically, the importance of this research focuses on understanding the significance and impact of social media platforms in shaping public opinion and directing society towards specific issues. Additionally, it aims to highlight the specific role of Facebook in mobilizing users around certain social issues, examine its relationship with public opinion formation, and consequently, its influence on various social issues and decisions.

The study seeks to understand how Facebook affects and has the ability to gather a large number of users in shaping and forming public social opinion.

⁴ Anwar Atazi, "Social Media: Public Opinion Shaping and Social Pattern Transformation," an article published on the Socialist Union website. [Online] Available at: <https://alittihad.info>.

Study Terminology:

➤ **Concept of Social Media:** Social media sites are defined as an electronic network system that allows users to create a personal account and then connect it through an electronic social system with other members who share similar interests, hobbies, or networks⁽⁵⁾. These sites enable communication between individuals in a virtual community, bringing them together based on common interests or affiliations⁽⁶⁾. Social media includes direct communication services such as messaging or viewing the profiles of others⁽⁷⁾. The internet has contributed to the creation of unconventional patterns of groups and social relationships that are not tied to identity, nationality, or geographical boundaries. These relationships form within the digital (cyber) space, unrestricted, undefined in features and dimensions, free, explicitly determined by those with common interests within a unified informational space⁽⁸⁾.

Rapid and successive developments facilitated the collection of information, especially after the "information revolution" in the last two decades. Internet sites and open message pages (allowing individuals to send messages available to anyone who enters the site) are forms of computer-derived data. Social media refers to interactive sites on the internet that allow users to open a page within a specific electronic social system, enabling them to communicate with each other through a virtual space where individuals come together for specific purposes. Notable among these sites is Facebook, which is the central focus of our research.

The concept of public opinion:

Mukhtar Al-Tahami defines public opinion as the prevailing opinion held by the majority of the conscious people within a specific period regarding one or more issues. It involves heated debates and discussions that directly affect the interests or human values of this majority⁽⁹⁾. Ismael Saad sees public opinion as the culmination of the thoughts, beliefs, and positions of individuals and societies towards issues that affect the social order. It includes individuals, organizations, and systems that can influence the social fabric through communication processes that may relatively or completely impact human society locally and internationally⁽¹⁰⁾.

Leonard Doob defines public opinion as "an expression of a specific issue discussed by a particular group⁽¹¹⁾." Ahmed Badr sees it as the "implicit agreement or consensus of a certain segment of society representing a certain degree of importance in facing a specific problem in a specific way."⁽¹²⁾ He further notes that public opinion is formed by the opinions of individuals representing the public in discussions. Ibrahim Imam defines it as the prevailing idea among the general public, connecting them with a common interest in a specific stance, action, or issue related to their common interests⁽¹³⁾.

In summary, public opinion shapes the direction that reflects the ideas and beliefs of a group on an issue or problem concerning the entire society. It represents a real force in society, expressing the viewpoint of the majority that can influence events positively or negatively, affecting the interests of the majority or common human values.

Public opinion does not necessarily mean unanimity among the majority or minority on a single opinion. It becomes public when the minority complies with the majority's opinion, and this

⁵ Rady Zaher, *The Use of Social Media in the Arab World*, Al-Tarbiyah Journal, Issue 51, Al-Ahliyya Amman University, Page 23.

⁶ Maryam Nareman Noumar, *The Use of Social Networking Sites and Their Impact on Social Relationships*, Supplementary Thesis for the Master's Degree, University of El-Hadj Lakhdar Batna, 2012, Page 44.

⁷ Hanane Bint Shashua Al-Shahri, *The Impact of Using Electronic Social Networks on Social Relationships – Field Study* – King Abdulaziz University, Saudi Arabia, 2013, Page 7.

⁸ Dr. Nadim Mansouri, *Sociology of the Internet*, 1st Edition, Forum for Knowledge, Beirut, 2014, Page 13.

⁹ Mukhtar Al-Tihami, "Public Opinion and Psychological Warfare," Dar Al-Fikr, Cairo, Egypt, 1974, p. 17.

¹⁰ Ismael Saad, "Public Opinion," Dar Al-Maaref, Beirut, Lebanon, 1979, p. 57.

¹¹ Ahmed Badr, "Public Opinion: Its Nature and Formation," Anglo Egyptian Library, 3rd edition, Cairo, 1987, p. 27.

¹² Ibrahim Imam, "Principles of Islamic Media and Practical Applications," Arab Thought House, Cairo, p. 362.

¹³ Mohamed Sabri Ahmed Youssef, "Public Opinion and Its Impact on Political Organization and Constitution Protection," Doctoral Dissertation, Faculty of Law, Ain Shams University, 1990, p. 24.

compliance is not forced or based on fear. Consensus is not required; instead, public opinion requires the satisfaction of the minority with the majority's opinion, based on conviction rather than coercion.

Through these definitions, we can discern general rules governing the public opinion:

1. Public opinion is an evaluative stance that an individual takes regarding a controversial issue.
2. It should be apparent, as the condition for public opinion is its expression.
3. It is characterized by dynamism and movement, meaning it responds to various life circumstances, distinguishing it from stable and unchanging beliefs.
4. Public opinion is a social product resulting from mutual communication among various groups and individuals in society, necessitating objective agreement and open discussion of the public opinion topic.
5. Public opinion takes its shape from the social framework within which it operates.
6. Public opinion represents the views of a large group of individuals, and these views are related to disputed issues and matters of common interest. However, these opinions do not exert influence on the behavior of individuals and political government groups.

Factors Influencing the Formation of Public Opinion:

Cultural Community Factor:

The customs, traditions, habits, ethics, arts, values, beliefs, ideas, and experiences constitute the most significant factors influencing the formation of public opinion.

Leaders in Society Factor:

This refers to the traditional and modern leaders in all societies who play a crucial role in shaping, changing, spreading, and intensifying public opinion.

Communication and Media Factor:

Undoubtedly, communication and its various tools have objectives aimed at influencing and changing people's positions and opinions to achieve the political and intellectual direction they adopt. The impact of media on public opinion is inherent, as every individual, whether educated or not, must engage with newspapers, radio, or television. In the current era, media and communication tools have diversified and changed, with the emergence of what is known as new media. With the rise of the Internet and the prominence of several social media platforms, these sites have a significant impact on shaping public opinion. Communication, especially in today's world, remains an influential and fundamental factor in forming public opinion.

Nature of Events Factor:

An event, whether termed an issue, problem, or subject for public opinion, fundamentally enters as an element among the components of public opinion. However, from another perspective, based on its nature, it will affect the directions of public opinion, its spread, intensity, and strength. If the nature of the event is ordinary, public opinion will be ordinary in its directions, strength, intensity, and spread. If the event is extraordinary, an extraordinary public opinion will result in its directions, spread, and intensity⁽¹⁴⁾.

Types of Public Opinion:

Considering one type of public opinion resulting from the noticeable evolution of media:

Electronic Public Opinion: This is a communicative message of the Internet, playing its role in viewing and being accessed by anyone who owns or can use that service. Simultaneously, individuals can access it at the same time as others using channels known as electronic opinion. It encompasses any

¹⁴ Amer Hassan Fayyad, "Methodological Introduction to Public Opinion and Human Rights," Dar Zahran for Publishing and Distribution, Jordan, 2007, p. 26.

idea, proposal, opinion, participation, or even an angry objection or joke expressing a specific orientation or defending a particular ideology. It follows from an individual or collective personal experience, reaching a general political outcome. In this case, electronic opinion represents all segments that have the means or technological tools for expression, communication, and discussion. If we express this digitally, we have in Egypt no less than 3 million Internet users. The formation of electronic public opinion is linked to two fundamental variables:

Education level, the presence of a communication network, and available internet services are interconnected with various sub-variables. These include the number of schools, universities, and scientific institutes, the availability of internet culture through them, and the level of education. The second variable is linked to the number of telephone lines, the strength of the existing network, the number of companies providing such services, as well as internet cafes or public places that offer such services, generally referred to as accessibility, free access, and speed.

Although the activities of the public that represent electronic public opinion are confined to the virtual world, it serves as an effective means of communication, discussion, exchanging opinions, educational processes, raising awareness, and a platform for the dissemination of globalization principles or opposition to them. Recently, the virtual realm has extended to become a stage for civil and revolutionary action in the real world through networking and coordination among activists.

Theoretical Perspectives of the Study:

Analyzing the role of social media in shaping public opinion on social issues requires concepts, theories, and tools that align with it. Theoretical frameworks consist of interrelated concepts, definitions, and issues that form an organized view of phenomena by defining the relationships between variables to explain the relationship between the interests and agendas of social networking platforms. The theoretical perspectives in this study include:

1. Technological Determinism:

Adherents of technological determinism believe that technology itself possesses the power to change the nature of social relationships and the social reality. Optimists argue that technology inherently brings progress to humanity, serving as a solution to real-world communication failures. Pessimists, however, view technology as a tool for imposing dominance and control over weaker populations, intruding into personal lives, and disrupting real-world social relationships⁽¹⁵⁾.

2. Social Determinism:

Social determinism theory asserts that social relationships are the foundation for creating social networking sites, acting as the driving force for establishing these platforms rather than the other way around⁽¹⁶⁾. Advocates of this theory argue that social relationships hold significant influence, compelling individuals to attempt to create an environment that unites them, constructing a unified framework through various applications on the internet, mobile devices, and mass media, aiming to bring people closer together, thus offering a perspective opposite to technological determinism⁽¹⁷⁾.

Previous Studies:

Numerous studies have been conducted on the topic of the proliferation of social media and its impact on societies. Here are some studies related to the research topic and the results they have yielded:

¹⁵ Social Problems in the Arab Society: School behavior, customary marriage, divorce, sexual deviance, internet addiction. Arab Organization for Administrative Development, 1st edition, 2013, p. 7.

¹⁶ Zaher Radi, "The Use of Social Networking Sites in the Arab World," Education Journal, Issue 15, Al-Ahliyya Amman University, Amman, 2003, p. 23

¹⁷ Dr. Abbas Mustafa Sadek, "New Media: A Study in its Theoretical Approaches and General Characteristics," The Arab Gateway for Media and Communication Sciences, 2011, p. 9.

1. Arab Studies:

- **Mohamed Al-Khalifi's Study (2002)⁽¹⁸⁾:** Titled "The Impact of Social Media on Society," this study reviewed the effects resulting from the use of social media and the Internet on society. It examined the benefits and both positive and negative impacts on users. The researcher applied the study to a sample of 412 students from the College of Engineering. The study found several negative effects resulting from prolonged use of social media, leading to addiction. However, it also identified a positive aspect, such as bringing individuals, especially youth and university students, closer together, aiding in their academic tasks and facilitating the exchange of ideas.
- **Halmi Sari's Study (2005)⁽¹⁹⁾** The study, titled "Internet Culture and its Role in Social Communication," had a comprehensive theoretical and practical approach to information technology. It explored the negative and positive impacts of using social media. The study, conducted on a group of Qatari youth in Doha (a sample of 539 young men and women), revealed that excessive use of social media is a common cause of psychological and social isolation. Continuous anxiety, frustration, and stress were identified as major symptoms. The study also noted dissatisfaction and complaints from the families of young people due to their withdrawal into social media usage, neglecting real social life with their relatives, leading to strain in family relationships.
- **Shuaa Al-Youssef's Study:⁽²⁰⁾** Titled "Benefits and Harms of Modern Technologies and their Negative Effects on Individual Health," this study focused on the impact of individual addiction to modern technologies and the internet on self-control, real social communication abilities, and personal well-being. The study highlighted the serious indicator of individuals' addiction to internet use and modern technologies. It emphasized that the widespread availability and usage, especially among university students, pose an escalated risk. The study underscored the need for attention to this point and the implementation of mechanisms to control and regulate the use of such technologies.

Secondly: Foreign Studies:

1. Krout et al. Study (2007)⁽²¹⁾:

Title: "The Impact of Internet Use on Social Interaction and Individual Mental Health."

Study Results: Indicated that increased internet use has a significant negative impact on social interaction and the ability to communicate with family. The study also suggested that prolonged sitting in front of a computer and using social media networks can lead to depression and social isolation.

2. Nie and Erbing Study (2009)⁽²²⁾:

Title: "Social Networking Sites and Society."

Study Focus: Explored the effects of excessive use of social networking sites, whether on the internet or through mobile applications, on an individual's ability to socialize with those around them. Results showed that the more individuals used social media, the less capable they were of socializing with relatives and friends.

¹⁸ Mohamed Bin Saleh Al-Khalifi, "The Impact of the Internet on Society: A Field Study," *Alam Al-Kutub*, Volume 22, Issues 5 and 6, pp. 469-502.

¹⁹ Halmi Sari, "Internet Culture: A Study in Social Communication," Majdalawi Publishing and Distribution, Amman, Jordan, 2005, p. 19.

²⁰ Shuaa Al-Youssef, "Modern Technologies: Benefits and Harms - A Study of Negative Effects on Individual Health," *Kitab Al-Ummah - Qatar*, Issue 112, 26th Year, First Edition, 2006.

²¹ Kraut, R., Lundmark, V., Patterson, M., Kiesler, S., Muko., T., and Scherlis, W. 2007. "Internet Paradox: A Social Technology that Reduces Social Involvement and Psychological Well-being". *Journal of American Psychologist* Sept., vol.53, No.9, p.1017-1031.

²² Nie, Norman and Erbing, Lutz. 2009. *Internet and Society: A preliminary Report*. Stanford Institute for the Quantitative study of Society. Intersurvey Inc., and Mckinsey and co.

2. Krout and Others Study (2011)⁽²³⁾:

Title: "Internet Use and Its Relationships with Social and Psychological Life."

Study Findings: Emphasized that individuals who excessively use the internet lack the happiness that real social relationships and face-to-face interactions with family and friends bring. The study highlighted that those addicted to social media experience frustration and severe depression, attempting to avoid social activities offered to them for entertainment, choosing instead to sit behind a computer screen for long periods without attempting to abandon this habit and open up new social horizons.

By reviewing these previous studies and their findings, it is evident that there is inconsistency in the results regarding the impact of social media on society. Most studies have focused on the negative effects of social media use, especially on university students. However, it is crucial to consider the positive impact of social networking sites on their users and the interconnectivity they foster. It should be noted that social media has a profound influence on all segments of society, not just university students. Nevertheless, society, with its diverse levels, classes, and categories, has become habituated to constant use of these platforms, making them an integral part of daily life. This aspect requires careful consideration, focused study, and the development of useful solutions to mitigate this phenomenon.

Theoretical Framework:

In contemporary times, digital communication and media have become essential life necessities. They serve as a crucial link connecting all components and institutions of social construction. Media shoulders the responsibility of conveying both positive and negative aspects of each social institution to others. Media plays a pivotal and delicate role in shaping public opinion by mobilizing universities around specific ideas, opinions, and trends. The free dissemination of information through digital social media platforms creates a significant potential for popular movements based on broad and accurate knowledge of political and social events. These platforms exert powerful influences on decision-makers in shaping public opinion⁽²⁴⁾.

Communication media act as a bridge between public opinion and decision-makers in society. Often, sensitive issues that are not covered by other media outlets are brought to the forefront through the boldness and freedom of expression of digital social media. There are numerous problems and issues in society that traditional media might overlook due to conflicts with the media owner's policy or because these issues might open doors to other problems, such as corruption issues, which digital platforms may address more extensively due to their freedom of expression and courage in tackling certain topics⁽²⁵⁾.

The impact of media on shaping public opinion varies depending on the communication environment through which reception processes occur. The effects differ between readable, visual, and audible media, each possessing distinct advantages that make them differ in terms of influence from other media. The repetition of exposure to communication media enhances their impact on shaping public opinion. Social media platforms have distinguished themselves with a powerful influence, combining the advantages of traditional media (readable, audible, and visual) in the messages they present. Therefore, there are two different directions in studying the impact of communication media:

1. Collective Level Direction:

- This links the changes occurring in public opinion at the collective level to the changes in the content of media messages. When communication media present different and conflicting

²³ Kraut, Robert, et al.; 2004. "The Internet and Social Participation Contrasting Cross-Sectional and Longitudinal Analysis". [Web page]. Retrieved July 24, 2006, from world wide web: <http://jcmc.Indiana.edu/vollo/issue 1/shklovshi-kraut.html>

²⁴ Thebsi, Abdul Kareem, and Atahat, Zuhair. "The Role of Social Media Networks in Shaping Public Opinion Among Jordanian University Students." *Journal of Political Science, Volume 40, Issue 1, Petra University, Amman, Page 74.*

²⁵ Mukhtar Al-Tahami. Previous Source, Page 21.

perspectives on a specific issue, measuring the impact of all these perspectives on public opinion becomes a challenging task.

2. Individual Level Direction:

- This explains the variance in the impact of media from one individual to another. The effects depend on a two-stage process: exposure to communication messages presented by media and the understanding of these messages (reception stage), and the acceptance of the content of these messages (acceptance stage). These processes are influenced by an individual's level of awareness⁽²⁶⁾.

There is no doubt that social media has become a hallmark of the era and a highly influential tool in shaping the thinking of societies. It is a double-edged sword, capable of promoting positive behavior within society by encouraging individuals to form friendships, explore new scientific advancements, exchange scientific experiences in all fields, and operate on all levels. However, it can also be a lethal weapon, undermining all the good values an individual should possess, turning them into an excessively aggressive personality by avoiding establishing natural social relationships with those around them, be it family, relatives, or friends.

Social Networking Sites:

There are several definitions specifically related to the concept of social networking sites, including:

- It is a network that includes a group of individuals with similar interests, inclinations, and a desire to form friendships through the use of the World Wide Web⁽²⁷⁾.
- Social networking sites can also be defined as "a system of electronic networks that allows subscribers to create their own site and then link it through an electronic social system with other members who share the same interests and hobbies."
- Furthermore, social networking sites can be described as a social café where individuals gather to exchange information with a distinction between the real café and the technological café, as the technological café can be carried anywhere⁽²⁸⁾.
- Social networking sites have been defined as social gatherings on the Internet where participants can engage in discussions during an open timeframe, united by a positive human feeling within a specific framework.
- Additionally, they have been identified as virtual communities on the Internet that bring together individuals sharing common interests, exchanging experiences and information through a specific program or application that they all use⁽²⁹⁾.

Types of Social Networking Sites:

Due to the proliferation of many social networking sites, it is challenging to enumerate all sites related to social interaction. Nevertheless, despite the multitude of sites, some stand out prominently in this field, including:

²⁶Zuheir Aabid. "The Role of Social Media in Shaping Public Opinion in Palestine." *Journal of Al-Najah University for Humanities, Issue 6, Volume 24, 2012, Page 142.*

²⁷ Dr. Bahaa Al-Din Mohammed Mazyad. "Virtual Communities as Alternatives to Real Communities - The Book of Faces as a Model." *United Arab Emirates University, 2012.*

²⁸ Dr. Ali Muhammad Rahouma, "The Internet and the Techno-Social System," Beirut, Center for Arab Unity Studies, 2007, p. 75.

²⁹ Jehan Haddad, "Electronic Cafés and Their Role in Cultural Transformation in the City of Irbid: An Anthropological Study." Yarmouk University, unpublished master's thesis, 2002.

1- Facebook⁽³⁰⁾:

Facebook⁽³¹⁾ is a social networking site that allows subscribers to communicate with each other through the use of site tools and establish connections and friendships. Individuals, whether real or considered entities like companies, organizations, or institutions, can register for free and engage in communication and interaction with others⁽³²⁾.

Some key features of Facebook include:

- a. The "Wall" feature, providing a dedicated space on a user's profile page where friends can send messages or write on the user's wall.
- b. The "Pokes" feature, allowing users to send a virtual poke to draw attention to each other, serving as a notification that a friend is welcoming them.
- c. The "Status" feature, enabling users to inform their friends about their current locations and activities.
- d. "Notes" or comments, a blogging-related feature allowing users to add tags and embed images, facilitating the incorporation or linking of blogs⁽³³⁾.

In addition, Facebook offers services such as messaging, chat, and sending virtual gifts.

2- Twitter⁽³⁴⁾:

Twitter is a social networking site that has significantly contributed to some important political events in various countries, both Arab and foreign. It focuses on sending short tweets that have had a profound impact on recent events. The size of the text messages sent by Twitter is limited to 140 characters per message.

Twitter emerged in early 2006 as a research development project conducted by the American company Obvious in San Francisco. It was officially launched for users in October 2006. Since then, the site has gained popularity as a new service in 2007, mainly known for providing microblogging services. In April 2007, Obvious separated the service from the company and established a new company named Twitter⁽³⁵⁾.

Motivations for Using Social Networking Sites⁽³⁶⁾: There are various motivations that drive individuals to use social networking sites, and these motivations vary in terms of goals and reasons. We will elaborate on these motivations as follows:

³⁰ Ihab Khalifa, "Social Networking Sites: Tools of Contemporary Change Online," Arab Group for Training and Publishing, First Edition, 2016, p. 114.

³¹ Mark Zuckerberg founded the website in 2004 when he was a student at Harvard University. Known for his keen interest in the Internet, Zuckerberg's goal was to design a site that would bring together his university peers, allowing them to exchange news, photos, and opinions while facilitating communication. The initial focus was not on creating a commercial site to attract advertisements. The site gained popularity among Harvard University students and quickly expanded to include students from other universities and high schools seeking to explore university life. Facebook remained exclusive to university and high school students for two years. In September 2006, Zuckerberg decided to open the site to the general public. Currently, Facebook has a diverse user base, supporting over 70 languages. The platform is not limited to individuals; many companies, organizations, and governments worldwide use it for marketing messages, charitable fundraising, customer and member communication, among other purposes.

³² Amina Adel Suleiman Al-Sayyed and Wahba Mohamed Khalifa, "Social Networks and Their Impact on Specialists and Libraries: A Comprehensive Study of the Presence and Use of Facebook," a research paper presented to the Egyptian Association of Libraries and Information, participating in the thirteenth conference for library and information specialists, Egypt, 2009, p. 18.

³³ Saleha Al-Damari, "Students and Social Networks: A Field Study on the Uses and Satisfactions of Students at the College of Arts and Media, Facebook as a Social Network," a research paper submitted to the College of Media, Al-Ahgaff University, Yemen, 2010, p. 8.

³⁴ The previous source, p. 118.

³⁵ Wikipedia, the Free Encyclopedia, available at: <http://ar.wikipedia.org>

³⁶ Khaled Ghassan Al-Muqaddadi, "The Social Media Revolution: The Nature of Social Networking Sites and Their Dimensions," Dar Al-Nafae for Publishing and Distribution, 1st edition, 2014, p. 35.

1. **Distance from Family and Relatives:** The geographical distance between family members and relatives, coupled with the necessity for some close individuals to travel for work or medical reasons, has led to the search for a method and means to communicate with these individuals. This has become a significant reason for resorting to the use of social networking sites.
2. **Family Issues:** Many individuals turn to using social networking sites as an escape from family issues occurring within the home. In an attempt to distance themselves from the stress, individuals seek out new friends as a way to break away from the tension.
3. **Lack of Job Opportunities:** A significant number of young people resort to social networking sites due to unemployment and the absence of job opportunities that allow them to channel their energy and capabilities into meaningful work. They turn to social networking sites to escape from the harsh reality of unemployment⁽³⁷⁾.
4. **Leisure Time:** Some individuals fill their leisure time by engaging in conversations with friends and forming new friendships. This is an attempt to eliminate feelings of boredom and the desire for renewal, creating a social atmosphere behind computer screens⁽³⁸⁾.

Conclusion:

The evolution of information and communication technology has provided humans with the opportunity to connect with each other to the extent of understanding their thoughts and opinions. With the recent rise of social media platforms, the world has transformed into a small village. From this development, social projects emerged, focusing on societal issues by shaping public opinion and influencing decision-makers under the impact of online crowds. Various segments turned to these virtual spaces to express their concerns, making this online platform a powerful and influential force.

The advantage of quick and instant interaction has redefined the notion that "the world has become a small village." Social media is now a new kitchen for creating and generating a new public opinion on various issues. It has become an effective tool that cannot be ignored, especially as it continues to attract a diverse audience of all ages and backgrounds.

The rapid and immediate interaction characteristic has brought an end to the prevailing saying, and now social media networks offer products, including ideas. Therefore, for governmental institutions and large companies entering this field and competing in it, they must realize this fact. They need to provide real products that appeal to the targeted audience's taste, interact with public opinion, and avoid relying on pre-packaged templates that the audience is no longer interested in.

One of the most important strategies used in shaping public opinion through social media networks is focusing on understanding the needs of the target audience. Crafting the product or idea and presenting it to the public in a way that engages them, allowing them to interact and share their opinions. This approach creates an open workshop for opinion-making, enabling organizations and companies to understand the community's trends and feedback on the presented product or idea. It offers a free service to entities, allowing them to closely monitor and interact with ongoing events in real-time.

In conclusion, it is essential for users to optimize their use of social media by promoting awareness and guidance to mitigate the growing impact of these platforms on personal aspects of society. Authorities should deter individuals who exploit social media for personal gain or harm to society. Governments should recognize the importance of platforms like Facebook as effective communication tools, leveraging them to address various issues. Implementing effective strategies to solve societal problems and shape public opinion is crucial. Moreover, users need to be aware of the broad impact of these platforms, especially their use for political purposes, incitement to violence, and other negative aspects. Harnessing the potential of Facebook as a tool for societal pressure to address various social problems is vital. Monitoring Facebook to curb abuses and mitigate negative impacts is crucial,

³⁷ Basem Al-Ja'abari, "The Internet and Social Networking Sites," Al-Rawad Publishing and Distribution, 1st edition, 2009, p. 121.

³⁸ The previous source, p. 121.

steering these platforms towards serving the public interest. Lastly, a comprehensive awareness program is needed to combat false information and encourage responsible behavior, cooperation, and ethical values within society.

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